

Plyometric Training on Selected Skills Fitness Among Collegiate Volleyball Players of Chiplun

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Abstract

As a result of the innovations brought by different sports sciences in the field of sports, now there are a number of scientific methods to improve each and every quality which determines the performance in each game and sports. Enhanced research activity in time with the rate of demand for each game and sports. Volleyball training and volleyball coaching needs to help to target the right muscles for fitness. Volleyball is a sport that requires a multitude of athletic abilities, such as physical fitness and volleyball skills. The objective of this research was to assess the skills in volleyball, namely, serve and attack for this study. And to find out the effect of plyometric training on skill variables of collegiate men volleyball players and to compare these effects with pre and post test to determine whether these training produced significant changes in the skill variable. The study proved that plyometric training improved selected skill variables like serve and attack of the collegiate men volleyball players of Chiplun.

Introduction

Sport training is the total process of preparation of a sportsman, through different means and forms for better performance. The Sports performance is the result and expression of the total personality of the sportsman. The educational aspect of sports training is unfortunately overlooked by coaches and teachers of physical education in India (Singh, H. 1984).

Plyometric training is one of the best methods of developing explosive power in sports. Basically, plyometrics provide a method of training for the optimum relationship between strength

and speed which will ultimately manifest in self as explosive power. Today plyometric movement are performed in almost all sports. Basic strength level must be attained before starting plyometric training programme. The choice of exercise must correspond to age, sex and biological development of sports person. These should be gradually increased during a complete training cycle. Body weight should be the determining factor in assigning the value of jumps in work out. Generally, the number of sessions to devote the plyometric training is 2 or 3 times per week.

Volleyball has developed into a highly competitive sport which requires a high level of physical, physiological and psychological fitness. The game at a high level of competition requires quicker sudden movements and fast reaction. Volleyball matches have no time limit and matches can last for several hours, if the teams are evenly matched. Players having more individual skills in the game can never assure victory. Speed helps to elevate the skills to higher levels of performance and endurance helps to sustain the skills effectively throughout a game. Excellence in sports and games calls for three factors' skills, speed and endurance as energy on one hand and efficiency in skills on the other. It would be absurd to cultivate skill only without developing speed and endurance, one without the other is bound to fail and in combination they have the way to excellence.

Material and Method

The purpose of the study is to find out the effect of plyometric training on selected skill fitness variable among collegiate men volleyball players of Chiplun. For this purpose, collegiate volleyball players who have participated at inter-collegiate level competitions were selected from different colleges in Chiplun. Twenty volleyball players in the age group of 19 to 23 were randomly selected as subjects for this study. Selection of variable researcher reviewed the various scientific literatures pertaining to plyometric exercises on selected skill variable in volleyball players from books, journals, and research papers. In dependent variable is serve and attack. Independent variable is plyometric training program. Pre-test was conducted for experimental group on the variables (2 skill variables) selected for the study, namely, serve and attack. Experimental groups underwent the respective training for 12 weeks. Immediately after the completion of 12 weeks training, all the subjects were measured of their posttest scores on the selected criterion variables. The difference between the initial and final scores was considered the effect of respective

treatments. To find out statistical significance of the results obtained, the data were subjected to statistical treatment using t-test.

Plyometric Training

The plyometric training programme was scheduled for six days (Monday to Saturday) per week in the morning between 6.30 a.m. and 7.45 a.m. for twelve weeks. The plyometric training programme consisted of warm up and stretching for 10 – 15 minutes, selected plyometric exercises and cool down for 5 – 10 minutes. The initial intensity was fixed at 80 – 85%. The intensity of the exercise was gradually increased, once in every four weeks. The intensity was fixed between 85% and 90% during 4-8 weeks and 90% and 95% during 8-12 weeks. The subjects were asked to perform 10 repetitions in each exercise and 90 seconds rest was given as recovery between sets.

Table no. 1
Training Plan

Sr. No	Exercises	Rest Between Sets
1	Squat Jumps	90 Seconds
2	Jump to Box	90 Seconds
3	Lateral Jump to Box	90 Seconds
4	Bounding	90 Seconds
5	Bounding with the rings	90 Seconds
6	Depth Jump	90 Seconds
7	Medicine Ball Chest Pass	90 Seconds
8	Box Drill with rings	90 Seconds
9	Medicine Ball Standing throw	90 Seconds
10	Lateral Hurdle Jump	90 Seconds

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained from the experimental groups before and after the experimental period were statistically analyzed with paired 't' test. The level of confidence was fixed at 0.05 level for all the cases.

Table no. 1
Statistical Analysis

Groups		N	Mean	SD	't' Value
Serve Skill	Pre-test	20	30.8	11.1	3.41
	Post-test	20	34.2	12.9	
Attack Skill	Pre-test	20	9.8	3.1	4.12
	Post-test	20	11.5	4.1	

The pre and post-test mean values of experimental group on volleyball skill serve and attack are graphically presented in below figure.

Graph no. 1

Discussion

In order to find out the effect of plyometric training on Serve and Attack skill the obtained pre-test and post-test means were subjected to paired sample t- test. The effect of Plyometric training on Serve & Attack is presented in table. The analysis of t-test proved that there was

significant difference between the pre test and post test as the obtained t- value 3.41 and 4.12 was greater than the required table F value to be significant.

Conclusion

It was found that plyometric training significantly improved volleyball skill, such as, serve and attack of collegiate men volleyball players compared to pre and post test. By comparison of experimental groups, it was found that plyometric training was significantly better to improving serve and attack skill.

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